

Control of Ink Color Variations in the Drying Period of Prints Created by Lithographic Printing

Thi Kieu Nguyen Hoang^{*1}, Hong Quyen Duong¹

¹*School of Materials Science and Engineering, Hanoi University of Science and Technology, Hanoi, 100000, Vietnam*

Abstract— The drying process of printing ink on paper substrates in offset printing is complex and significantly affects ink density and color. This study examines the changes in ink density and color from the moment of printing until the ink is fully dry. Experimental analysis reveals a non-linear relationship between wet and dry ink densities, with variations depending on the type of ink and initial density levels. The study proposes a method for controlling ink color by taking real-time density measurements directly at the printing machine. By establishing empirical relationships between wet and dry ink densities, operators can predict and control the final color outcome more accurately, ensuring adherence to industry standards. This method offers a practical solution for enhancing color accuracy in the printing process.

Keywords— Ink density, Ink color variations, Offset printing, Drying time, Color control

I. INTRODUCTION

The drying process of printing inks on substrate materials is a complex and extended procedure, particularly in offset printing technology, where ink can take several hours or even days to dry completely, depending on specific conditions [1]. It is observed that the color properties of ink (lightness, blue-yellow, red-green content, density) differ when the ink is still wet compared to after it has completely dried [2]. These color changes are influenced by various factors such as printing technology, ink characteristics, substrate surface, and environmental storage conditions [3].

Several studies have investigated these phenomena. Research on inkjet printing has provided insights into drying time and its impact on print quality [4][5]. In the realm of offset printing, Csaba Horvath et al.[3] used a simulated offset printing machine to explore the changes in color values of Sun Sunchemical SunLit Intense Process inks on three different print media types. They found that color changes occur rapidly during the first 500 seconds, with the rate of change slowing as the ink dries, stabilizing around 2000 to 2500 seconds. Similarly, Erdoğan Köse's study [6] with the Komori Lithrone Offset Printing Machine and uncoated paper showed that complete dryness is achieved within 48 hours. Initial changes are minimal in the first half-hour, with significant increases starting after the 45th minute. These differences in published results stem from the varying conditions of the printing machine, ink, and paper, as the interaction between the ink and paper and their drying mechanisms are distinct.

During the printing process, operators often struggle to predict these color changes in the ink layer, making it difficult to accurately control the color on the print sheet. Determining the point at which the ink layer is completely drying is crucial for operators to assess color reproduction accurately [7]. Moreover, operators typically use a densitometer or visual inspection to evaluate the amount of ink transferred to the substrate, corresponding to ink densities. However, without a density standard, printing standards evaluate color based on color values such as those in the CIE Lab system [8]. Therefore, there is a need for an effective solution that allows operators to assess color accurately during the printing process.

This study investigates the effect of ink drying time on the color values of the ink layer on the print sheet within a specific printing system. The research aims to determine when ink can be thoroughly dried on the substrate and predict the post-drying color characteristics. Based on these findings, we propose a method for controlling color through density measurements during printing.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

A. Printer and printing process

The experiments were carried out using a Heidelberg SM 74-2 colors offset printing machine, as shown in Fig. 1. Offset printing inks Nippon speed (Cyan - C, Magenta - M, Yellow - Y) and coated papers 150 g/m² were used. The environmental conditions were controlled with a humidity of $65 \pm 2 \%$ and a temperature of $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. 1 Offset printing machine SM74 -2 (2012)

Fig. 2 CMYK test target

The experiment consists of two parts. The first part involves examining the changes in density and color over time, from the moment the print leaves the machine until 24 hours post-printing. The second part investigates the changes in ink color corresponding to variations in density, establishing the relationship between wet and dry ink density. This relationship will predict the color characteristics once the ink is dry.

In each experiment, the test form Altona Test suite 1.1 (Fig. 2) was used for evaluations. The printing process was calibrated to allow a unique density in all printed areas and all printed sheets (~ 300 sheets)

B. Color measurement

The solid densities were measured by an X-Rite SpectroDensitometer 504, Inc. Grandville, MI. Device repeatability was 0.01 – 0.02

The CIELAB color coordinates of the printed samples were measured according to ISO 12647-1 standard on an X-Rite DTP22 Color Digital Swatchbook Spectrophotometer under D50 illuminant, 2° observer, 0/45 or 45/0 geometry, white backing.

In CIELAB space (Fig. 3), the lightness value, L*, varies from 0 (black) to 100 (white). The a* and b* coordinates correspond to the green-red and yellow-blue color axis, respectively, where negative values indicate a shift toward green and blue and positive values signify a shift toward red and yellow.

Fig. 3 CIELAB color space (source:[7])

The color difference was calculated by

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{\Delta L^2 + \Delta a^2 + \Delta b^2}$$

Where ΔL, Δa, Δb are the difference between the measured and the referred samples of L*, a*, and b*, respectively.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Primary color changes during drying time

This study examined the changes in color density over the drying time of primary color inks C, M, Y, and K. Measurements were taken right after printing (1 minute) up to 24 hours post-printing. The printed samples were stored under room conditions with 65 ± 2% humidity and a 25 ± 2 °C temperature. The results are reported in Table 1 and Fig. 4.

TABLE I
COLOR DENSITY CHANGES THROUGH THE DRYING PERIOD

Time (min)	Solid density			
	C	M	Y	K
1	1.51	1.43	1.15	1.78
10	1.50	1.40	1.14	1.73
30	1.48	1.40	1.14	1.69
60	1.45	1.39	1.11	1.67
90	1.45	1.34	1.11	1.55
180	1.46	1.35	1.11	1.56
240	1.45	1.35	1.11	1.56
1440	1.45	1.35	1.12	1.54

Fig. 4 Color density changes as a function of drying time

The color density changes insignificantly over the drying period, except for black ink. Generally, density tended to decrease as the inks dried. The percentage differences in density between measurements carried out just right and 24 hours after printing are 4.26%, 5.80%, 2.37%, and 13.51% for C, M, Y, and K, respectively. The complete drying time for all ink layers is determined to be 90 minutes, which corresponds to when no further density changes can be observed (see Fig. 4).

The color changes (L^* , a^* , b^* values) and the color difference ΔE_{ab} between the wet and dry states of the ink layers are presented in Table II. The color differences are noticeable to the naked eye for all colors ($\Delta E_{ab} \geq 2$). The change is more significant for Black ink, with $\Delta E_{ab} > 8$. The result is that Black ink typically contains fine carbon black particles or other colorants. Thus, black ink may penetrate the paper more deeply, altering how the ink is distributed on the paper's surface. Consequently, changes in the L^* , a^* , and b^* values and color density are more noticeable as the ink dries.

TABLE III
CIE LAB COORDINATES CHANGE DURING THE DRYING PERIOD

	Time (Min)	L^*	a^*	b^*	ΔE_{ab}
C	1	45.66	-31.86	-30.79	2.82
	90	46.7	-29.32	-30.13	
M	1	40.92	57.28	3.69	3.65
	90	41.52	53.74	3.02	
Y	1	75.8	-7.98	78.66	3.66
	90	78.59	-8.43	76.34	
K	1	13.45	-2.01	8.42	8.02
	90	19.28	3.34	9.75	

B. Color changes with ink density.

In this series of experiments, the L^* , a^* , b^* color values were investigated as a function of density. The results for the four primary CMYK colors are reported in Table 2. It is important to note that the

measurements were conducted on thoroughly dried ink layers. The color differences ΔE_{ab} , were calculated against the referred colors specified in ISO 12647-2 standard using the paper type PS1 [8]. The required deviation tolerance is smaller than 3 for CMY and less than 5 for K.

It was observed that the color difference for CMYK colors varies significantly based on density levels. Achieving the desired color within ISO standards requires maintaining the ink density within specific ranges. The appropriate density range for each color to meet the ISO 12647-2 standard is depicted in Fig. 5 and detailed in Table 4.

TABLE III
CIE LAB COORDINATES CHANGE DURING THE DRYING PERIOD

	Measured sample			Referent sample			ΔE
	L*	a*	b*	L*	a*	b*	
D_C	C						
1.52	44.58	-35.75	-29.60	48.18	-34.05	-30.84	4.17
1.50	46.08	-36.09	-29.74				3.13
1.49	46.20	-36.07	-29.97				2.96
1.46	47.30	-35.59	-29.23				2.40
1.42	47.34	-36.26	-28.87				3.08
1.40	47.68	-36.29	-27.74				3.86
D_M	M						
1.49	40.12	60.65	3.40	41.18	63.55	4.89	3.43
1.46	40.88	62.82	2.38				2.63
1.40	41.32	61.46	2.92				2.88
1.38	42.28	59.71	2.91				4.46
1.35	42.55	61.11	2.65				3.58
1.32	43.13	59.95	0.18				6.24
D_Y	Y						
1.18	75.94	-7.40	85.56	77.27	-6.51	87.69	2.66
1.13	77.71	-7.31	89.23				1.79
1.10	78.25	-5.83	83.21				4.64
1.09	78.13	-6.23	82.33				5.44
1.04	78.56	-6.12	81.39				6.44
1.01	79.20	-6.51	80.05				7.88
D_K	K						
1.76	13.81	0.37	8.67	13.99	-0.23	2.70	6.00
1.75	13.92	2.39	1.41				2.92
1.70	13.96	1.28	5.89				3.53
1.63	14.36	0.59	7.47				4.85
1.57	17.68	-0.35	9.71				7.92
1.53	19.28	3.34	9.75				9.51

Fig. 5 ΔE is plotted as a function of color density

C. Relationship between wet and dry ink densities

The relationship between wet and dry ink densities is presented in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6 Relationship of wet and dry ink densities

This relationship is not linear for all inks. This implies that density constantly changes as the ink layer dries compared to just after printing. However, the change is inconsistent among different inks and varies at various density levels. For example, an ink layer of Cyan with an initial density (D_c) of 1.4 remains at 1.4 when dry, but an initial density of 1.8 changes to 1.56 (see Fig. 6). This result indicates that predicting density changes mathematically is not feasible. Thus, it is necessary to establish this relationship empirically to control density during printing.

Based on the experimental results shown in Fig. 6, the density ranges for wet ink were determined to correspond to the required densities for dry ink. These values represent the target densities for the printing process. The results are reported in Table 4.

TABLE IVV
DENSITY RANGE OF WET AND DRY INKS

Density	C	M	Y	K
Dry ink	1.45 ± 0.05	1.44 ± 0.04	1.14 ± 0.04	1.70 ± 0.07
Wet ink	1.44 ± 0.06	1.46 ± 0.06	1.28 ± 0.03	1.89 ± 0.05

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study highlights the complexities involved in the drying process of printing ink on a paper substrate, particularly within the context of offset printing technology. It has been demonstrated that ink density and color significantly change from printing until the ink is fully dry. Through experimental analysis, it was found that the relationship between wet and dry ink densities is non-linear, varying across different inks and density levels.

This study proposes a method for directly controlling ink color through density measurements at the printing machine. By establishing empirical relationships between wet and dry ink densities, operators can predict and control the final color outcome more accurately, ensuring compliance with industry standards.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. A. El-Rahman, E. Saad, C. Aydemir, S. A. Özsoy, and S. Yenidogan, "Drying methods of the printing inks," *J. Graph. Eng. Des.*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 29–37, 2021, doi: 10.24867/JGED-2021-2-029.
- [2] T. Şahinbaşkan and E. Köse, "Modelling of time related drying changes on matte coated paper with artificial neural networks," *Expert Syst. Appl.*, vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 3140–3144, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.eswa.2009.09.068.
- [3] C. Horvath and P. Görgényi-Tóth, "Study of Colour Change in the Course of Drying on Prints Created Using Offset Printing Technology," no. November 2018, pp. 323–332, 2018, doi: 10.24867/grid-2018-p39.
- [4] L. Carreira, L. Agbezugbe, and A. Gooray, "Correlation between drying time and ink jet print quality parameters," *Proc. IS&T's Int. Congr. Av. Non-Impact Print. Technol.*, pp. 334–337, 1995.
- [5] M. Ciquino *et al.*, "Effect of surface tension and drying time on inkjet-printed PEDOT:PSS for ITO-free OLED devices," *J. Sci. Adv. Mater. Devices*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jsamd.2021.09.001.
- [6] E. Köse, "Determination of color changes of inks on the uncoated paper with the offset printing during drying using artificial neural networks," *Neural Comput. Appl.*, vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 1185–1192, 2014, doi: 10.1007/s00521-014-1602-4.
- [7] B. C. K. Ly, E. B. Dyer, J. L. Feig, A. L. Chien, and S. Del Bino, "Research Techniques Made Simple: Cutaneous Colorimetry: A Reliable Technique for Objective Skin Color Measurement," *J. Invest. Dermatol.*, vol. 140, no. 1, pp. 3–12.e1, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jid.2019.11.003.
- [8] INTERNATIONAL STANDARD ISO 12647-2, *Graphic technology — Process control for the production of halftone colour separations, proof and production prints — Part 2: Offset lithographic processes*, 2013